

Action of Sulphur Containing Inhibitors on the Corrosion of 63/37 Brass in Acetic Acid Solutions

M. M. PATEL, N. K. PATEL R. S. SHAH and J. C. VORA

Chemistry Department, University School of Sciences, Gujarat University, Ahmedabad-9
and Chemistry Department, M. G. Science Institute, Ahmedabad-9

Manuscript received 22 March 1971 ; revised 4 August 1973 ; accepted 17 June 1974

Nitrogen and sulphur containing organic compounds are considered as potential inhibitors for corrosion of metals and alloys in acid media. Acetic acid is moderately corrosive to brass. Practically few references are available on the inhibitive power of sulphur containing compounds towards brass. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to evaluate the inhibitive power of 2-mercapto-benzothiozole, *p*-thiocresol and diphenylthiourea towards corrosion of brass by acetic acid solutions.

Experimental :

Brass specimens of composition Cu-63.2%, Zn-36.6%, Sn-0.07% and Pb-0.01% were cold rolled and annealed at 550°. Rectangular specimens of size 3 × 6 cm (26 S.W.G) were used. Preparation, testing procedure, and cleaning of the specimen were same as described earlier¹ 250 ml of the solution was used for immersion of each specimen. All experiments were carried out at $0^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}$. 2-Mercapton-benzothiozole, *p*-thiocresol and diphenyl thiourea have been used as corrosion inhibitors in 0.1 *N* and 0.5 *N* acetic acid solutions for 5 and 10 days duration. Results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1. 63/37 BRASS (3 × 6 CM) IN ACETIC ACID WITH INHIBITORS

Concentration of inhibitor (%)	Loss (mdd)	0.1 <i>N</i> Acetic acid						0.5 <i>N</i> Acetic acid					
		Cu/Zn Ratio		Inhibition (%)	Cu/Zn Ratio		Inhibition (%)	Cu/Zn Ratio		Inhibition (%)	Cu/Zn Ratio		Inhibition (%)
		5 Days	10 Days		5 Days	10 Days		5 Days	10 Days				
Blank	21.5	3.0	—	22.2	2.5	—	27.8	2.6	—	24.1	2.5	—	
<i>p</i> -Thiocresol													
0.002	12.7	2.8	41	17.9	2.6	20	12.2	2.3	56	22.3	2.7	7	
0.004	0.55	—	97	0.78	—	96	1.16	—	96	14.6	2.4	39	
0.008	0.17	—	99	0.53	—	98	0.44	—	98	0.92	—	96	
0.012	0.05	—	99	0.53	—	97	0.17	—	99	0.78	—	97	
0.02	0.3	—	98	6.5	2.3	71	2.77	2.7	90	9.1	2.1	62	
<i>MBT</i>													
0.002	11.3	2.5	48	7.33	1.9	67	11.8	2.3	57	7.83	2.8	67	
0.004	0.44	—	98	0.28	—	99	1.0	—	96	1.42	2.3	94	
0.008	0.22	—	99	0.17	—	99	0.72	—	97	0.75	—	97	
0.012	0.17	—	99	0.11	—	99	0.22	—	99	0.28	—	99	
0.02	0.17	—	99	0.08	—	99	0.22	—	99	0.19	—	99	
<i>Diphenyl thiourea</i>													
0.004	4.0	2.3	82	2.64	2.5	88	17.9	2.4	35	15.4	2.7	36	
0.008	3.5	2.1	84	2.58	2.6	88	13.9	2.3	50	15.2	2.5	37	
0.016	2.9	2.1	85	2.49	2.1	89	12.9	2.1	54	14.5	1.9	40	
0.024	2.9	2.0	87	2.28	1.9	90	11.9	2.1	57	14.4	2.0	40	
0.04	2.77	1.9	87	2.19	2.0	90	10.1	2.3	63	13.9	2.3	43	

Results and Discussion :

2-Mercapto-benzothiozole (MBT) forms a slight blackish brown visible film on the metal plate. The film was not easily removable by 5% sulphuric acid, the solution remained colourless. After cleaning, the plate turned slight black. MBT gave 98% protection at its 0.004% concentration. There was decuprification in most of the cases. Diphenyl thiourea gave good inhibition at its 0.004% concentration. Its inhibition increased with its concentration. Plate remained bright yellow after cleaning. In 0.5 *N* acetic acid, it had a tendency to form a visible, thick spongy film on the metal plate which was difficult to remove by 0.5% sulphuric acid. After cleaning, the plate was slight blackish dull yellow. The alloy mostly dissolved as a whole. Its inhibitive power slightly decreased in 0.5 *N* acetic acid. *p*-Thiocresol gave more than 98% protection at its 0.012% concentration in 0.1 *N* acetic acid for 5 days duration. At its higher concentration (0.02%) it formed a loose film. Percentage efficiency observed with this inhibitor was independent of the duration and the concentration of the acid. However, the efficiency slightly decreased at its higher concentration (0.02%). There was decuprification throughout in most of the cases.

Sulphur containing organic compounds are considered to be excellent complex or chelate forming substances with metals of transition series^a. Such substances or their salts with transition metals are strongly film forming substances providing a barrier between the metal surface and the corrosive medium.

2-Mercaptobenzothiozole is believed to be anodic inhibitor for copper^a. It forms extremely adherent, highly insoluble film with copper ions at the surface of the metal. The p^ka value of MBT is reported to be 7.6 ± 0.1^a ; hence the dissociation of the -SH group decreases until it can be considered to be completely undissociated at pH values less than 6. In aqueous solution it ionizes as a weak acid.

The ionic species forms insoluble salt with metal ions like copper. This forms protective coating on the metal surface. Over and above ionized sulphur group, MBT also contains a ring nitrogen, both capable of forming co-ordination bonds with metals or the metal ion.

MBT gives insoluble precipitates with copper ions over a very wide range of the concentrations of both copper ions and the reagent in acetic acid medium. It can be concluded, therefore, that the inhibitive power of MBT can be assigned to the formation of a protective film over the metal surface.

Thiourea and its substitutes are excellent complex forming compounds particularly with copper^b. It is a unidentate chelate and forms strong complexes with copper¹. Diphenyl thiourea forms an insoluble complex with copper in acetic acid. The inhibitor contains both sulphur and nitrogen as donor atoms and so it can utilize either of them as donor atoms. It can also act as bidentate ligand. It is not possible to assign any definite account of its low inhibitive power in the 0.5 *N* acid compared to the 0.1 *N* acid. However, it is apparent that low inhibitive power is certainly due to increase in thickness of the film rendering it more porous and penetrable by the corrosive agent. *p*-Thiocresol contains only sulphur as a donor atom to the metal and thus can form a complex which is very stable at both the concentrations of the acid. It forms a thin and strongly adherent film on the metal surface initially which provides excellent inhibition for shorter duration. Its efficiency, however, decrease somewhat with increase in duration if more amount of it is added due to thickening of the film. Thiocresol, like MBT, acts as a weak monofunctional acid.

Acknowledgement :

Our thanks are due to late Dr. A. M. Trivedi, Professor of Chemistry, University School of Sciences, Gujarat University for his interest in the work.

References :

1. M. N. Desai and A. M. Trivedi, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1960, 23, 9.
2. C. A. Mann, A paper presented at the sixtyninth general meeting, held at Cincinnati, Ohio, April 23, 1936.
3. J. L. Powell, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1959, 51, 75A.
4. L. N. Lomakia and E. K. Yakovskaya, *Vestn. Mosk-Univ. Khim.* 1967, 24157-73-6 Russ.
5. L. Carlin, "Transition Metal Chemistry", Pub : Marcel Dekkert, New York, 1969, Vol. 5, p. 142.